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Effect of Heating on Selected Fish (Tilapia and Catfish) Properties during Drying

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Research Article

Effect of Heating on Selected Fish (Tilapia and Catfish) Properties during Drying

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to determine the effect of heating on selected fish properties. Two samples were used (tilapia and catfish). The samples were given different treatments and dried using gas, coal, and firewood. Fish dried with coal was found to be the best in terms of texture. However, in terms of odour, colour and oil in excess gas, dried fish was found to be the best. Also ANOVA was carried out for the ten panelists to determine the difference in the mean for the different selected fish properties.

Keywords: Tilapia, Catfish, Drying.

INTRODUCTION

Fish is a very important foodstuff in developing countries, in areas where cold preservation techniques are often missing. Quality losses can occur very rapidly after catch leading to spoilage due to factors such as moisture, microbial growth, oxygen and temperature.

Drying of fish has become of key interest due to the gap between the demand and supply of fish as a result of increase population, lack of processing and storage facility, poor post harvesting, handling, utilization of unconventional fish species.

For instance, in Nigeria as at 1994 estimated fish demand was put at 1,139,833 tones based on the population figure of 94,986,044 and per capital consumption of 12kg which globally was considered for normal health growth, however, only about 280,309 tonnes were produced indicating a deficit of 14,705,737 (FAO,1999).

Water activity measures the availability of water in fish flesh (Jason, 1958). Drying means extraction of water from the fish by heating (Arason et al., 1992). Also the preservation of fish by salting and drying is achieved by lowering the water activity (a_w) of the fish flesh (Ismail and Wooton, 1992).

The effects of different processing and cooking methods on nutritional compositions of different species of fish have been studied. Nutritive and organoleptic changes of Nigerian traditionally processed fresh water fish species were studied by Afolabi et al. (1984). The effect of traditional drying processes on the nutritional values of fish was studied by Eves and Brown (1993). The proximate and mineral composition of dried salted roes of hake (*Merluccius Merluccius L*) and ling (*Molva Molva L*) were reported by Rodrigo et al. (1998). Tao and Linchun (2008) reported influence of hot air drying and microwave drying on nutritional and odorous properties of grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*).

It has been observed that different processing and drying methods have different effects on the organoleptic parameters on the nutritional composition of fish due to heating, freezing and exposure to high concentration of salt which changes the chemical and physical concentration, leading to increase in digestibility and protein denaturation. The objectives of this study is to determine the effect of heating on selected fish (tilapia and catfish) properties during drying using different drying methods.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The fish samples, tilapia fish (*Oreochromis Niloticus*) and catfish (*Arius sp.*) were bought from creek road market in Port Harcourt. The samples were cleaned (descaled and degutted) and was washed thoroughly to remove blood and slime.

Experiment

Samples were weighed and recorded; the volume of the sample and the surface area were taken as well. The fish were divided into two equal parts. One part cured with fish and the other without curing. Each of the two parts were subdivided into three equal parts.

The first part was dried using a gas-fired oven at 230°C, the second part was dried with firewood, and the third part was dried with a local oven fired with charcoal. The total drying time was recorded for each treatment methods.

The volume, weight and surface area of the dried fish were also taken. The percentage shrinkage and moisture content of the fish was calculated.

Sensory Evaluation: This was taken to determine the taste, odour, colour, texture and oil in excess of dried fish. A panelist of ten member were given to score the product on scale of 5=Excellent, 4= very good, 3=Good, 2 = Fair and 1= poor for taste.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The sensory assessment as judged by ten panelist for tilapia and catfish respectively were shown in table 1 and 2. Fish dried using coal were found to be the best in terms of texture with an average score of 2.3 and 2.8 for tilapia and Catfish respectively. Clifford et al. (1980) observed that the extent of dried fish texture, toughness and dryness is greatly influenced by loss of moisture during drying and protein denaturation effect.

For other parameters such as odour, colour and oil in excess, the panelist scored gas-dried fish better than those of coal and firewood. However, in terms of taste, it was found that salted products were generally scored higher than the unsalted products.

The volume and weight of both tilapia and catfish were compared before and after the drying as shown in graph below.

Table 1: Sensory evaluation of dried tilapia fish

Sample	Sources of energy	Selected Parameters				
		Texture	Odour	Taste	Oil in excess	Colour
1	Gas	4.2	5	4.2	2.6	3.9
2	Firewood	4.2	4.2	4	3	2.7
3	Coals	4.2	3.8	4.9	3	4.3
4	Gas	4.2	3.1	1.8	3	2.9
5.	Firewood	4.2	3.4	2.4	3	4.2
6	Coal	4.2	3.4	2.3	3	3.7

Table 2: Sensory evaluation of dried catfish

Sample	Sources of energy	Selected Parameters				
		Texture	Odour	Taste	Oil in excess	Colour
1	Gas	3.0	4.4	3.9	2.5	4
2	Firewood	3.0	4.4	4	3	2.4
3	Coals	3.6	4.1	3.9	3	3.3
4	Gas	4.0	3.7	3.2	3	3.5
5.	Firewood	3.4	3.8	2.8	3	2.0
6	Coal	3.0	2.1	2.0	3	3.3

Tables above shows the average values of ten panelist.

Table 3: Panelists' scores on colour of tilapia fish

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	5	3	4	3	4	5	24
2	5	2	5	5	3	4	24
3	4	3	5	5	3	4	24
4	3	2	5	4	3	3	20
5	4	2	4	5	4	4	23
6	3	4	4	5	2	3	21
7	4	3	4	4	2	3	20
8	4	3	3	4	3	3	20
9	3	3	5	4	3	4	22
10	4	2	4	3	2	4	19
TOTAL	39	27	43	42	29	37	217
MEAN	3.9	2.7	4.3	4.2	2.9	3.7	

Analysis of variance on colour of tilapia

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	5.1	9	0.56	0.53	0.84	2.10
Samples	2.9	5	0.59	0.55	0.74	2.42
Error	47.7	45	1.06			
Total	55.7	59				

Table 4: Panelist score on taste (tilapia)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	5	4	5	2	2	2	20
2	4	5	5	3	2	2	21
3	5	4	4	4	3	3	23
4	5	4	4	3	2	2	20
5	4	3	5	3	2	2	19
6	3	4	4	3	3	2	19
7	4	3	5	2	2	2	18
8	4	4	4	3	3	3	21
9	5	5	5	2	3	3	23
10	3	4	5	3	2	2	19
TOTAL	42	40	46	28	24	23	203
MEAN	4.2	4	4.6	2.8	2.4	2.3	

Analysis of variance on taste

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Judges	4.3	9	0.48	1.38	0.23	2.10
Samples	50.1	5	10.02	28.62	0.00	2.42
Error	15.8	45	0.35			
Total	70.2	59				

Table 5: Panelist scores on texture (tilapia)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	5	4	5	3	5	4	26
2	4	5	4	4	4	5	26
3	4	4	4	5	5	5	27
4	4	4	5	5	3	4	25
5	3	3	5	4	3	5	23
6	5	3	4	5	3	4	24
7	4	4	4	4	3	3	22
8	5	3	4	3	4	4	23
9	4	3	5	4	5	5	26
10	4	4	5	5	3	4	25
TOTAL	42	37	45	42	38	43	247
MEAN	4.2	3.7	4.5	4.2	3.8	4.3	

Analysis of variance on texture

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Judges	4.0	9	0.45	0.86	0.57	2.10
Samples	4.7	5	0.94	1.79	0.13	2.42
Error	23.5	45	0.52			
Total	32.2	59				

Table 6: Panelist scores on odour (tilapia)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	4	4	5	3	4	4	24
2	5	5	4	5	3	3	25
3	4	4	5	4	4	5	26
4	5	4	3	3	4	4	23
5	4	3	3	4	3	5	22
6	4	4	3	3	5	3	22
7	5	5	3	3	4	3	23

Table 6 Continues

8	4	4	4	4	3	3	22
9	4	5	5	4	3	4	25
10	5	4	3	4	3	5	24
TOTAL	44	42	38	37	36	39	236
MEAN	4.4	4.2	3.8	3.7	3.6	3.9	

Analysis of variance on odour

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	3.1	9	0.34	0.59	0.80	2.10
Samples	4.7	5	0.95	1.64	0.17	2.42
Error	25.9	45	0.58			
Total	33.7	59				

Table 7: Panelist score oil in excess (tilapia)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	1	3	3	3	1	1	12
2	3	3	1	3	1	1	12
3	1	1	3	3	3	3	14
4	1	3	3	1	3	3	14
5	3	1	1	3	3	1	12
6	3	1	3	1	1	3	12
7	3	3	1	1	3	1	12
8	1	1	1	3	3	3	12
9	3	3	3	3	3	1	16
10	1	3	3	1	3	3	14
TOTAL	20	22	22	22	24	20	130
MEAN	2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.4	2	

Analysis of variance oil in excess

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	3.0	9	0.33	0.28	0.98	2.10
Samples	1.1	5	0.23	0.19	0.97	2.42
Error	54.2	45	1.20			
Total	58.3	59				

Table 8: Panelists' scores on colour (catfish)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	5	3	4	3	2	3	20
2	4	2	3	5	3	3	20
3	3	3	5	4	2	4	21
4	4	2	4	3	2	4	19
5	4	2	3	3	2	3	17
6	5	3	3	3	3	2	19
7	4	2	4	4	3	4	21
8	4	4	4	4	4	3	23
9	3	2	3	3	3	3	17
10	4	3	4	3	2	4	20
TOTAL	40	26	37	35	26	33	197
MEAN	4	2.6	3.7	3.5	2.6	3.3	

Analysis of variance on colour

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	5.0	9	0.56	1.22	0.30	2.10
Samples	16.7	5	3.34	7.33	0.00	2.42
Error	20.5	45	0.46			
Total	42.2	59				

Table 9: Panelists' scores on taste (cat fish)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	4	4	5	4	3	2	22
2	5	5	5	3	2	3	23
3	5	4	4	3	3	3	22
4	3	4	3	4	3	2	19
5	4	3	4	4	2	3	20
6	3	4	3	2	4	2	18
7	4	3	3	3	3	2	18
8	4	4	4	2	3	2	19
9	3	5	4	2	3	2	19
10	4	4	4	3	2	2	19
TOTAL	39	40	39	30	28	23	199
MEAN	3.9	4	3.9	3	2.8	2.3	

Analysis of Variance on taste

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Judges	4.8	9	0.54	1.16	0.34	2.10
Samples	25.5	5	5.10	11.09	0.00	2.42
Error	20.7	45	0.46			
Total	51.0	59				

Table 10: Panelists' Scores on texture (Cat Fish)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	4	3	4	4	4	5	24
2	3	5	4	5	3	4	24
3	4	3	4	4	3	5	23
4	5	4	5	4	4	3	25
5	3	3	4	4	3	4	21
6	4	3	3	4	4	4	22
7	5	3	4	5	4	3	24
8	3	5	4	4	3	4	23
9	4	4	5	4	4	3	24
10	3	4	4	4	4	3	22
TOTAL	38	37	41	42	36	38	232
MEAN	3.8	3.7	4.1	4.2	3.6	3.8	

Analysis of Variance on texture

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Judges	2.3	9	0.25	0.52	0.85	2.10
Samples	2.7	5	0.55	1.12	0.36	2.42
Error	21.9	45	0.49			
Total	26.9	59				

Table 11: Panelist score on odour (cat fish)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	4	5	4	5	4	3	25
2	5	3	5	4	5	4	26
3	4	4	3	4	4	4	23
4	5	5	4	3	3	4	24
5	4	3	4	4	4	5	24
6	4	3	5	3	3	4	22

Table 11 Continues

7	5	4	3	3	4	5	24
8	4	5	4	3	3	5	24
9	4	3	5	4	4	3	23
10	5	4	4	4	4	5	26
TOTAL	44	39	41	37	38	42	241
MEAN	4.4	3.9	4.1	3.7	3.8	4.2	

Analysis of variance on odour

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	2.5	9	0.28	0.50	0.87	2.10
Samples	3.5	5	0.70	1.25	0.30	2.42
Error	25.0	45	0.56			
Total	31.0	59				

Table 12: Panelist score on oil in excess (cat fish)

Panelists	Samples						Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1	3	1	1	1	3	3	12
2	3	1	1	3	3	3	14
3	1	3	3	3	1	3	14
4	3	1	3	3	3	3	16
5	1	3	3	3	3	1	14
6	3	3	3	1	3	3	16
7	3	1	1	3	1	3	12
8	1	3	1	1	3	1	10
9	1	3	3	3	1	3	14
10	1	1	3	3	3	3	14
TOTAL	20	20	22	24	24	26	136
MEAN	2	2	2.2	2.4	2.4	2.6	

Analysis of variance on oil in excess

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Judges	5.1	9	0.56	0.53	0.84	2.10
Samples	2.9	5	0.59	0.55	0.74	2.42
Error	47.7	45	1.06			
Total	55.7	59				

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

Sensory assessment as judged by the panelist is presented in tables 1 and 2 for tilapia and catfish respectively. It was observed that fish dried using coal were found to be the best in terms of texture, with an average score of 2.3 and 2.8 for tilapia and cat fish respectively. As stated by Clifford et al. (1980) that the extent of dried fish texture, toughness and dryness is greatly influenced by loss of moisture during drying and protein denaturation. The gas-dried fish was scored better in terms of its odour, colour and oil in excess. As regard the taste, the salted products were generally scored higher than the unsalted products.

CONCLUSION

It can be conclude that the methods of handling and heating during drying gas has a great influence on the fish quality (texture). Fish dried with coal has better texture when compared to those dried with gas and firewood. For other selected parameters such as odour, colour and oil, fish dried with gas was preferred.

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